

From photons to fish, from seconds to centuries; Generating FAIR data from high resolution sensors in the Western Channel Observatory

D2- Requirements and Architecture Document

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Constructing Digital Environments

Executive Summary

The Western Channel Observatory (WCO) is an oceanographic time-series and marine biodiversity reference site that provides a valuable source of data to a wide range of UK research, policymaker, public and businesses communities. Recently, emerging and innovative sensor and platform technologies have proven their abilities to increase both the spatial and time resolution of these data. While this additional data will allow current applications to evolve and improve their capabilities, a new generation of innovative digital solutions such as digital twins or higher level artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) applications require the creation of new, scalable, robust and mature data pipelines that focus on the need to make data truly findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

This short project has allowed a collaboration among data providers, data users and data archiving centres to investigate approaches to increase the FAIR-ness of marine observation data. Throughout this project, Constricting Digital Environment (CDE) Expert Network members and teams from Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML) and the National Oceanographic Centre (NOC) including the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC), have worked together, during two formal workshops and a large number of focused sessions, to build upon existing standards, tools and lessons learned to identify improved ways of working with marine observation data. This document, focusing on the development of improved time-series data architectures and requirements, presents outputs that span four main areas:

1. *Improved tools to **find** and explore data (FAIR) – The design of intuitive and interactive tools that allow users to find explore and provide feedback on the enriched metadata within complex and long-running data series.*
This architecture guides the development of visual, intuitive and interactive toolsets, available to all data users, to search data, interact with enriched metadata, discover and identify data of interest.
2. *Improving data **access** (FAIR) – The design of a common interface that allows data users to seamlessly access the BODC's archive and WCO's near-real time data within a single, intuitive interface.*
Prototypical tools developed within this project prove the concept that a data access ticketing system can enable users to accessed both archived and near real-time data through a single, seamless, structured and auditable data access process.
3. *Approaches to improving data **interoperability** (FAIR) – Designing approaches that encourage the use of shared metadata vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.*
Including the use of the MEDIN discovery metadata, increased use of standardised vocabularies and improved metadata richness.
4. *Increasing data **reusability** (FAIR) – A documented approach to enhancing the visibility of metadata and increasing its quality early in the data lifecycle.* Data reusability has been enhanced with the development of interactive user quality and provenance reporting tools, coupled with intuitive ways of displaying data provenance.
5. *The description of a maintainable and persistent **reference architecture** that encourages the sharing of best practice among projects support the design of future time-series digital environments.*
The reference architecture described in this document provides a reusable template that can guide the creation of FAIR marine observation data sets across a range of future digital environments. With a focus on maximising the value of marine observation data, this standards-based, modular and scalable Reference Architecture provides a solid foundation upon which future projects can efficiently build their designs, embed the use of common standards and vocabularies while providing a main table baseline that can be efficiently updated to capture lessons and share best practice from around the marine observation community.

As a first of three deliverables from the WCO CDE short project, this document (Deliverable D2) provides further descriptions of each of these outputs with the Marine Observation Data Reference Architecture provided for use within the wider marine observation data community provided in Annex 1. In addition, the WCO Profiler/CTD Data Target Architecture has been a core input to the implementation and test phases of the project, with the results reported in the planned Test Report and Summary of Developed Functionalities document (Deliverable D3). An overview of the complete project (Deliverable D1) will be presented at events such as the NERC Digital Gathering 2023 conference [1].

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The WCO is an oceanographic time-series and marine biodiversity reference site in the Western English Channel. The WCO measures several key parameters that are important to the functioning of the marine ecosystem such as light, temperature, salinity and nutrients. WCO's L4 station is a UN Ocean Decade-recognised biomolecular observation site and has some of the longest time-series of data in the world for zooplankton and phytoplankton monitoring. The WCO also incorporates the E1 station, providing a hydrographic data series dating from 1903. The complete WCO data set provides a digital resource that benefits scientists, policymakers, businesses, communities and individuals. The majority of these long time-series of data have been sampled at a weekly resolution at fixed locations. While this approach has been successful in developing the current set of impactful WCO data, emerging and disruptive sensor and platform technologies are increasing both spatial and time resolution of these data; with the potential for significant increases in value of these data for the UK's scientific, policy making and business communities by supporting responses to acute events while also better informing understanding of long-term environmental change. These high resolution data has the potential to provide real value to digital twins, allowing improved interconnection of observational data with models digital solutions including machine-to-machine (M2M) data transfer, higher level artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms. The challenge associated with achieving this potential however, lies in the need for data pipelines to continue to make data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) [2] as the size, frequency and complexity of these data series increases.

This short project, aligning with the NERC Constructing Digital Environment (CDE) programme goals, aims to use FAIR data principles to maximise the impact of new, high resolution marine sensing technologies as they are deployed to augment existing and future time-series data sets.

1.2 Document Scope

This report is deliverable D2 (*Requirements and architecture document*), as described in the Constructing Digital Environments Project Proposal Form [3]. In line with standards-based development methodologies [2] and to support the future maintenance and upgrade of the developed toolsets, this report documents the elicitation of requirements and develops a linked, structured target architecture. Delivered in a multi-community model-based format, the architecture is intended to be made available to other community members and provides support to the design of future digital architectures that support the creation of FAIR time-series data sets. This report contains three main sections; developing the project aims, objectives and high level requirements; the design of a generic Reference Architecture and, finally; the design of improved FAIR data elements within Western Channel Observatory (WCO) profiler and conductivity, temperature, and depth (CTD) data architecture.

2 Developing the project Aims, Objectives and High Level Requirements

2.1 Architecture and Requirements Structure

In line with standards-based development methodologies [2] and to support the future maintenance and upgrade of the developed architectures and toolsets, this project will elicit requirements from the identified project aims and develop a linked, structured target architecture. Delivered in a multi-community model-based format [3] [4], the architecture will be made available to other community members and may for the basis of future digital reference architectures. The framework followed to develop and document the project requirements is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Requirements Structure

2.2 Project Aims

The project aims and objectives were clearly set out in the project proposal form [3]. A summary of the content and links between the project aims and objectives is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Overview of the project aim and objectives

A key concept within the project aim is to improve the impact of data sets by developing the FAIR-ness of the data. A clear definition of how to make data FAIR can be found in the framework that forms the GoFAIR [5] principles, an overview of which is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Summary of the GoFair principles.

To achieve this aim, two linked objectives were identified; 1) Make data findable with scalable and tailored data visualisation and 2) Provide a ticketing system to improve data access and impact monitoring.

2.2.1 Project Objective 1 – Make data findable with scalable and tailored data visualization

Improved findability of the WCO data is achieved by implementing a suite of custom data visualisations that allow users to explore and interact with enriched discovery and usage metadata sets. Existing plots, hosted on the WCO website allow users to view data on specific days throughout the lifespan of the WCO. This project focuses on transitioning and expanding these capabilities in an improved, scalable architecture that is suited to high-resolution and multi-sensor data collection. Specifically, improvements create a suite of dynamic, web-based data visualisation tools that give users greater flexibility with customising plotting dates and variables. This is achieved by embedding widgets within a webpage which allow the user to select variables, dates of interest, data aggregations and plot types. Once the user has used the available tools to find a subset of the times and parameters of interest, additional tools support

the user through the process to access and download the data, streamlining the process and improving the accessibility of the data (links to Project Objective 2).

2.2.2 Project Objective 2 - Ticketing system to improve data access and impact monitoring

Improved accessibility of the WCO data will be achieved by implementing a custom data request form within the WCO webpage. This data request form, embedded within the data visualization tools (links to Project Objective 1), will guide users through a streamlined data request process. Once the user fills out the details of the form relating to their project and specific data request, emails to the appropriate data stewards, pre-populated email requests are automatically forwarded to the appropriate data stewards for processing. This structured data ticketing system will simplify the user’s data request process while simultaneously allowing the WCO data stewards to improve the speed at which data requests are handled. In addition, the availability of a simplified and clearly defined data request process will ensure that data access quality, regulation (e.g., GDPR) and traceability will remain scalable as new sensing technologies come online. Additionally, this functionality is expected to support the creation of a comprehensive, centralised database of data requests that will increase the completeness and accuracy of WCO data usage and impact analyses to be made.

Links between each of the objectives and the GoFAIR principles are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Links between the project objectives and the GoFAIR principles

Objective	Findable	Accessible	Interoperable	Reusable
<i>Project Objective 1</i> Make data findable with scalable and tailored data visualization	The data exploration tools should allow the user to identify the required data set at a granular level.	The data exploration tools should allow links to the data to be made using standard communications protocols.	Emphasis should be placed on the visibility of metadata to encouraging data creators to use standardised, shared vocabularies	Emphasis should be placed on the visibility of metadata fields so that data creators and users can increase the quality or metadata standardisation.
<i>Project Objective 2</i> Ticketing system to improve data access and impact monitoring	Data request tools should clearly define the data of interest.	Data request procedures should be open, free and common across organisations.	Data downloads should provide standards-based metadata.	Data access interfaces should clarify usage conditions.

2.3 Epic User Stories

2.3.1 Identified Epic User Stories

In order to design effective interfaces and implement tools that efficiently enable the project objectives to be implemented, an analysis of the future data users should be developed. By considering data users at this stage of design, the resulting tools and processes should focus on maximising the impact of the WCO data. The outputs of this analysis resulting in the identification of a wide number of parties interested in contributing and using data, from scientists to technology developers and members of the public. The main, high level interactions of each of these user groups has been summarised in a series of Epic User Stories that, by following industry best practice in agile development [8], will support the agile development activities within this project. Specifically, an Epic User Story supports the development of requirements by providing a short written request from the perspective of an end user. The structure of this request is pre-defined so that development teams can analyse the Epic User Story and develop their own, smaller User Stories that will drive development and implementation activities. A summary of each of the epic user stories is provided in a series of Use Case Diagrams in Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 4 - Epic User Story 1

Figure 5 - Epic User Story 2

Figure 6 - Epic User Story 3

Figure 7 - Epic User Story 4

2.3.2 Epic User Story Analysis

Important because it makes sure the developed capabilities align with the needs of the community. Analysis of links shown summarized in Table 2.

Note: Throughout Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4, the ■ symbol is used to identify a link between the column and row content.

Table 2 – Analysis of the users that will benefit from each of the architecture elements.

User Group (Who will benefit from the improvements?)		Related Epic User Story			
		Epic User Story 1	Epic User Story 2	Epic User Story 3	Epic User Story 4
Data Contributors	WCO Team	■	■	■	■
	Observatory Staff	■	■	■	■
	PML Scientists				■
	Local Scientists	■	■	■	
External Data Users	External Data Users	■	■	■	
	Local Scientists				■
	External Researchers				■
	External Funders				■
	Application Developers				■
	Members of the public				■
Data Archive Centres	BODC				■

A summary of the links between the identified epic user stories and the project objectives is provided in Table 3.

Table 3 – Analysis of the users that will benefit from each of the architecture elements.

Epic User Story	Related Objective	
	Objective 1	Objective 2
Epic User Story 1	■	
Epic User Story 2		■
Epic User Story 3		■
Epic User Story 4	■	■

In addition to describing the aims and objectives of the project, the project proposal [3] details the project's measures of success. For the project to succeed, the capabilities described in the four epic user stores must satisfy each of the measures of success. To ensure coverage, the link between the identified epic user stories and the success criteria identified in the WCO CDE project proposal [3] are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 – Analysis of the users that will benefit from each of the architecture elements.

Objective	Measures of Success	Related Epic User Story			
		Epic User Story 1	Epic User Story 2	Epic User Story 3	Epic User Story 4
Objective 1: Make data findable with scalable and tailored data visualization	External users shall be prompted to select start dates, end dates and variable(s) of interest via embedded widgets to create a visualisation of available data.	■			■
	External users shall be guided through the data download process, using parameters configured in the drawing regions of the plot.	■			■
	The visualisation tools should include an intuitive representation of key metadata values (e.g. A traffic light Red, Amber, Green (RAG) representation of data quality values).		■		
Objective 2: Ticketing system to improve data access and impact monitoring	External users shall be prompted to fill in all details of the request form and submit a data request.	■		■	
	External users should be prompted to tag any suspected data quality issues against a subset of data.		■		
	The data request form shall auto-populate based on current selections made within the data visualisation tools (Objective 1).	■			
	Data stewards shall be automatically notified, based on the variables of interest that are selected in the form.	■		■	■
	A database shall record requests so impact analyses may be made.		■	■	■

3 Developing a Reference Architecture for FAIR Marine Observational Data

The architecture that will define the tools developed within this project is progressed in line with software engineering best practice [2]. This guidance introduces the concept of Reference and Target architectures. A target architecture provides a framework around which the functionalities and capabilities required for a project can be efficiently developed and tested. In addition, a reference architecture provides a common, reusable framework that can be used to develop multiple architectures with capabilities related around a central theme. The Reference Architecture developed within this project provides the CDE community with a persistent and re-usable baseline upon which lessons learnt can be maintained and best practice can be developed in relation to the FAIR-ification of a wide range of time-series data sets. The role of reference and target architectures is summarised in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Overview of the links between Reference and Target Architectures

In addition to following guidance that supports the efficient development of software applications, this project has also complied with external guidance on making data FAIR, aligning with the GoFair FAIR-ification process [6], summarized in Figure 9.

Figure 9 – Activity diagram of the GoFair FAIRification process [6]

Each of the FAIRification steps have been followed in the creation of a reference architecture. Specific considerations at each stage are provided in section 3.1 to section **Error! Reference source not found.**

3.1 Retrieve and analyse the retrieved data

At the commencement of each project, the data that is to be made FAIR should be obtained and defined. This data may be any marine time-series data set. The output of this step should be a clearly defined boundary around the data of interested, including a description of its most granular data set.

3.2 Define the semantic model

By using Model-based systems engineering (MBSE) approaches [3] [4], the definition of a semantic model is contained within the developed reference architecture. A first iteration of this reference architecture is provided in Annex 1. The reference architecture’s model forms a basis upon which a consensus view of FAIR marine time-series data set design and best practice can be developed. The reference architecture can be used to identify existing, similar models that can be used to provide a robust and community accepted foundation to the development of new models, including links to existing vocabulary hierarchies and external standards. The reference architecture resources allow the classification of data models and data items in multiple research institutes to construct a coherent digital environment using common terms, views and data structures.

3.3 Make the data linkable and assign a licence

The obtained data should be hosted at a suitable set of locations that allow for; 1) the capture of near-real time data and 2) the long-term archival of data. Clearly, the need for time-series data to be available in near real time, perhaps before data quality checks have been completed, and for the data to be frozen and uniquely identifiable provides conflicting requirements. To mitigate this, an architecture is proposed that allows near real-time data to be accessed from an early stage within the data pipeline, while supporting users in the access of historic data from data archive centers. This architecture should be transparent to the end users, who simply find and access the data of interest. A summary of the proposed architecture is provided in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – Activity diagram showing the automated access of seamlessly accessing near real-time and archived data sets

3.4 Define metadata for the dataset

The metadata for a marine time-series data set should uniquely and richly describe the data. As shown in Figure 11, the metadata should consist of two main elements; Discovery metadata and usage metadata.

Figure 11 - Overview of Discovery and Usage Metadata

Further details about the content of each of these data sets in all anticipated marine time-series data sets is provided in section 3.4.1 and section 3.4.2.

3.4.1 Discovery Metadata

Discovery metadata contains key information that describes the dataset so that it can be found with standards based discovery services. A suite of discovery metadata standards are available, spanning from ISO 19115:2014 [10] which forms the basis of geographic data metadata standards, such as INSPIRE [8], GEMINI [9] and MEDIN [10], that provide regional and discipline specific extensions. Due to wide acceptance within the marine data community and the alignment with higher level standards, the reference architecture includes the use of the MEDIN Discovery Metadata standard. A summary of the discovery metadata elements required to describe a dataset is provided in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Overview of the MEDIN discovery metadata content

3.4.2 Usage Metadata

Fewer applicable standards exist to define the correct content of marine usage metadata. Following discussions among the project partners, a minimum metadata set for marine time series data has been defined and described in Figure 13. Within this mode, parameter names and codes should be recorded along with the data and should utilise the content of the NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) [11].

Figure 13 - Minimum usage metadata structure

3.5 Deploying the FAIR data resource

3.5.1 Maintaining Data Quality

A two-way communication of data quality can be designed that allows known data errors to be communicated to the data users while simultaneously allowing data users to report suspected errors to the data owners.

3.5.2 Legal Compliance

Managing data requests and maintaining details about who accessed the data requires the architecture to handle personal information in compliance with the UK's implementation of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [11]. A summary of GDPR protection principles that must be considered in any future data access ticketing systems are provided in Figure 14.

Figure 14 - Summary of GDPR considerations in the design of data request ticketing systems

4 Developing a Target Architecture for FAIR WCO Data within the CDE Project

The target architecture described in section 3 provides a framework to support the development of a range of marine time-series data sets. The WCO instantiation that will be developed within this project, documenting further, dataset specific information is described in this Target Architecture. Each of the reference architecture elements, structured by the GoFair FAIR-ification process, are expanded within this report to provide requirements that will drive the development of the project's toolsets.

4.1 Retrieve and analyse the retrieved data and define the semantic model

The WCO's situ measurements are undertaken weekly at coastal station L4 and fortnightly at open shelf station E1 using the research vessels in addition to data collected from buoys and a network of coastal observatories. These data record parameters that describe air, water column and benthic domains.

Within these data sets, the CTD and profiler sensor samples are currently taken on a weekly basis at two locations. It is anticipated that autonomous platforms and sensors will increase the temporal and spatial resolution of these data. As such, the CTD data within the WCO has been selected as the dataset that will be the focus of this project. A summary of the CTD sensor data parameters, shown within the complete set of WCO parameters, is provided in

Figure 15.

Figure 15 - Overview of the complete WCO data architecture with a focus on CTD data that will be improved in this project.

4.2 Make the data linkable and assign a licence

Currently, WCO's CTD data are sampled on a weekly basis and stored in a database hosted at PML. On a periodic basis, sets of these data are supplied to BODC who verify the metadata and archive the dataset. As a data user, it is often not clear how to access the required data and the location of recent data (e.g., data sampled 12 months before the request) as it may be stored at either PML or BODC. This route of sampling near real-time data and periodically storing a data set at a data archive centre, described in Figure 16, is a common architecture for time-series data sets and may provide an opportunity for the data user's experience to be improved.

Figure 16 – Activity diagram of the existing data archiving process

Specifically, this project will aim to prototype a seamless data request process that allows users to explore the data, identify the data they need and request an automated download of the data from wherever it is stored. This will provide data users with a single point of access for WCO data, automatically accessing data from either the most suitable near real-time or archived data locations throughout the data product's lifecycle. An overview of the proposed data access is provided in Figure 17.

Figure 17 – Activity diagram of an improved, seamless data request process

4.3 Define metadata for the dataset

4.3.1 Discovery Metadata

To aid the data users' ability to find the required data, the increased standardisation of discovery metadata is proposed. Building upon existing WCO data descriptors, the proposed discovery metadata associated with the CTD data set is detailed in Table 5. This discovery metadata set is intended to comply with the MEDIN Discovery Metadata standard [16] which, by design, is also compliant to the EU INSIRE and UK GEMINI discovery metadata standards.

Table 5 – An Example of Proposed CTD Discovery Metadata

MEDIN Discovery Metadata Field	Example Value
Resource Title	L4 - UK CTD profile data
Alternative Title	Western Channel Observatory CTD Data
Resource Abstract	Profile measurements taken at the L4 sampling point in the Western English Channel.
Resource Type	Series
Resource locator	https://www.westernchannelobservatory.org.uk/data/CTD/L4/131217_I4.asc (To be updated to BODC location once data archived)
Web Link to General Site	https://www.westernchannelobservatory.org.uk/
Unique Resource Identifier	PML20230625I4
Resource Language	eng (English)
Topic category	oceans
Keywords	Depth(m); Temperature(°C); Salinity(PSU); Density(kgm-3); Transmission,PAR (uEm-2s-1); Turbidity (NTU); Chl a,Fluorescence (no unit); Oxygen (uM); Sound Velocity (m/s); Salinity of the water column; Temperature of the water column; Marine; Oceanographic features; UK project.
Geographic bounding box	[50.39286954874358,-4.030023205012236; 50.28067303471916,-4.285455333918509]

MEDIN Discovery Metadata Field	Example Value
SeaVox Regions	English Channel (Western English Channel and Celtic Sea)
Vertical extent information	minimumValue: 2 maximumValue: 50 (Water Column)
Spatial reference system	https://epsg.org/crs_4326/WGS-84.html
Temporal reference	28/03/2023
Lineage	Data from CTD profiles using Seabird 19+ CTD, CTG MiniTracka Chl fluor., CTG PAR sensor, Wetlabs C-Star (red), SBE dissolved Oxygen. All files have been processed using the software and guild lines provided by Sea Bird Electronics Inc. CTD
Limitations on public access	CC BY 4.0
Conditions applying for access and use	Data is freely available for research or commercial use providing that the originators are acknowledged in any publications produced.
Responsible party - Owner	PML (forinfo@pml.ac.uk)
Responsible party - DataPOC	Tim Smyth (tjism@pml.ac.uk)
Responsible party - MetadataPOC	Thomas Mansfield (tma@pml.ac.uk)
Data Format	csv, delimited
File Identifier	131217_I4.asc
Metadata date	28/03/2023
Metadata standard name	MEDIN
Metadata standard version	3.1
Metadata language	Eng

The discovery metadata described in Table 5 has been validated with the MEDIN discovery metadata generator toolset, an output of which is provided in Annex 3.

4.3.2 Usage Metadata

To increase the interoperability and reusability of the data, standards-based usage metadata has been selected from within the NVS [11]. Specifically, the parameters selected were within the NERC P01 Parameter Usage Vocabulary (PUV) and are summarized in Figure 18.

Add instrument serial number too - Arbitrary thing in our own system SSN Schema. (W3 OGC standard <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>)

Figure 18 – Composite diagram showing the relationship between the usage metadata

Further information about each of the usage metadata fields is provided in Table 6 with additional parameters described in Table 7.

Table 6 - Further information about the identified usage metadata fields

Parameter Reference	Measurements (NVS Preferred Label)	NVS Alternative Measurement Label	NVS Label Vocabulary	NVS measurement identifier	Units (NVS Preferred Label)	NVS Alternative Unit Label	NVS Unit Identifier	NVS Unit Vocabulary
Depth	Depth (spatial coordinate) relative to water surface in the water body by profiling pressure sensor and conversion to seawater depth using UNESCO algorithm	CmpDep	P01	DEPHPR01	Meters	m	ULAA	P06
Temperature	Temperature of the water body by CTD	WC_temp_CTD	P01	TEMPST01	Dimensionless	Dmnless	UUUU	P06
Salinity	Practical salinity of the water body by CTD and computation using UNESCO 1983 algorithm	P_sal_CTD	P01	PSALST01	Litres per kilogram	l/kg	UKLG	P06
Density	Conversion factor (volume to mass) for the water body by CTD and computation of density (in-situ potential temperature surface pressure) reciprocal from pressure, temperature and salinity	Vol2MassCTD	P01	TOKGPR01	Percent	%	UPCT	P06
Transmission at Depth (m)	Transmittance (red light wavelength) per 25cm of the water body by 25cm path length red light transmissometer	Trans_red_25cm	P01	POPTDR01	MicroEinsteins per square metre per second	uE/m ² /s	UMES	P06

Parameter Reference	Measurements (NVS Preferred Label)	NVS Alternative Measurement Label	NVS Label Vocabulary	NVS measurement identifier	Units (NVS Preferred Label)	NVS Alternative Unit Label	NVS Unit Identifier	NVS Unit Vocabulary
PAR (uEm-2s-1) or Turbidity (NTU) at Depth (m)	Downwelling 2-pi scalar irradiance as photons of electromagnetic radiation (PAR wavelengths) in the water body by 2-pi scalar radiometer	Dwirr_2-piPAR	P01	IRRDPP01	TBC	TBC	TBC	P06
Chl a at Depth (m)	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	Volts	V	UVLT	P06
Fluorescence (no unit) at Depth (m)	Raw signal (voltage) of instrument output by in-situ chlorophyll fluorometer	FIVolt	P01	FVLTZZ01	Percent	%	UPCT	P06
Oxygen (uM) at Depth (m)	Saturation of oxygen {O2 CAS 7782-44-7} in the water body [dissolved plus reactive particulate phase] by Sea-Bird SBE 43 sensor and computation from concentration using Benson and Krause algorithm	O2_Sat_SBE43	P01	OXYSSU01	Meters per second	m/s	UVAA	P06
Sound Velocity (m/s) at Depth (m)	Sound velocity in the water body by computation from temperature and salinity by unspecified algorithm	Cmpval	P01	SVELCA01	Dimensionless	Dmless	UUUU	P06

Table 7 - Additional information maintained in the usage metadata

Additional Info (NVS Preferred Label)	NVS Additional Info Label	NVS Additional Info Identifier	NVS Additional Info Vocabulary
Bottle firing sequence number	FireSeqNo	FIRSEQID	P01

Note: The additional information described in Table 7 is required when discrete samples are taken instead of profile measurements.

4.4 Deploying the FAIR data resource

4.4.1 Maintaining Data Quality

In addition to directly increasing the FAIR-ness of the WCO data, this project aims to implement some practical first steps to allowing the on-going quality of the data to be monitored and reported. A high level overview of a proposed data quality framework, with key areas of carrying out automated data checks and providing users the ability to highlight poor quality data, is provided in Figure 19.

Figure 19 – Activity diagram providing an overview of the key data error reporting workflows

The result of automated data checks should be visualised in an intuitive way when users view the data. By checking data against a framework of pre-defined limits, the visualisation should identify any erroneous data sets by displaying them on colour coded plots or annotating the displayed data with a warning that the data may be invalid.

In addition to a framework of automated error checking, the data visualisation tools should allow data users to identify and report suspect data. A focus on this activity should be in making the reporting of suspect data as low overhead as possible, likely within two clicks. This requirement is motivated by the fact that, upon finding

erroneous data, many users may leave the resource to find more suitable data and are unlikely to complete detailed questionnaire about any issues observed.

4.4.2 Legal Compliance

To ensure GDPR compliance of the data request and impact aspects of the proposed architecture, an analysis of the applicability of the regulations has been applied to the data that is likely to be collected through each of the data request routes. The results of this analysis are provided in Figure 20.

Figure 20 - Applicability of GDPR regulations against each of the data collected.

This analysis identified that some of the data collected via the planned Custom Data Request form, part of the data access workflow, could be subject to GDPR. The design of the questions and tick boxes that relate to this data should reflect GDPR principles (e.g., the need to 'opt in' to privacy policies and agreement to future contact). As part of meeting the requirements of GDPR, a data lifecycle has been designed and provided in Figure 21.

Figure 21 – GDPR data maintenance timelines and rationale

Finally, a record of the personnel and legal entities that the data may be shared with is depicted in Figure 22. The requirement to share data with these groups should be communicated with the data user at the point of request submission within the implemented architecture.

Figure 22 - Diagram indicating who the data may be shared with throughout the data lifecycle

5 Conclusions and Next Steps

This short project has allowed a collaboration among data providers, data users and data archiving centres to investigate approaches to increase the FAIR-ness of marine observation data. This deliverable, *D1 - Requirements and Architecture Document*, summarises design notes, rationale and decisions made during discussion among Constricting Digital Environment (CDE) Expert Network members and teams from Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML), British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) and National Oceanographic Centre (NOC), made during two formal workshops and a large number of focused sessions, to build upon existing standards, tools and lessons learned to identify improved ways of working with marine observation data. This document is intended to directly inform the development of improved time-series data architectures and within PML and elsewhere in the CDE community, with outputs that span four main areas:

6. *The design of improved tools to **find** and explore data (FAIR) – The design of intuitive and interactive tools that allow users to find data and explore its enriched, associated metadata within complex and long-running data series.*
This architecture guides the development of visual, intuitive and interactive toolsets, available to all data users, to search data catalogues, discover and identify data of interest.
7. *Workflows that improve data **access** (FAIR) – The design of a common interface that allows data users to seamlessly access the BODC's archive and WCO's near-real time data within a single, intuitive interface.*
Prototypical tools developed within this project prove the concept that a data access ticketing system can enable users to accessed both archived and near real-time data through a standardised, seamless, structured and auditable data access process. This project has also taken steps to increase the standards compliance, quality and persistence of the metadata, allowing a sharable description of the data to be maintained even if the data is not available.
8. *Approaches to improving data **interoperability** (FAIR) – Designing approaches that encourage the use of shared metadata vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.*
Including the use of the MEDIN discovery metadata, increased use of standardised vocabularies and improved metadata richness.
9. *Increasing data **reusability** (FAIR) – A documented approach to enhancing the visibility of metadata and increasing its quality early in the data lifecycle.* Data reusability has been enhanced with the development of interactive user quality and provenance reporting tools, coupled with intuitive ways of displaying data provenance. In addition, the design of the ticketing and data request elements of the architecture focus on providing clear, concise and timely descriptions of data licencing and citation guidance. To ensure compliance with standards, the metadata created within this project has been validated within widely used community tools.
10. *The description of a maintainable and persistent **reference architecture** that encourages the sharing of best practice among projects support the design of future time-series digital environments.*
The reference architecture described in this document provides a reusable template that can guide the creation of FAIR marine observation data sets across a range of future digital environments. With a focus on maximising the value of marine observation data, this standards-based, modular and scalable Reference Architecture provides a solid foundation upon which future projects can efficiently build their designs, embed the use of common standards and vocabularies while providing a main table baseline that can be efficiently updated to capture lessons and share best practice from around the marine observation community.

Prototypical toolsets that implement the requirements described in this document are currently in development. A description of the developed functionalities and their compliance with the target architecture requirements described in this document will be provided in deliverable *D3 – Test Report and Summary Of Developed Functionalities*. *This document is an initial issue and may be updated as additional lessons are observed and learnt.*

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Annex 1- The Developed Reference Architecture

The reference architecture developed throughout this project is embedded within the Enterprise Architect [12] file below. Additional formats of the architecture are available upon request to tma@pml.ac.uk.

TimeSeriesReferenceArchitectureV1_0.xml

Annex 2 - Record of the WCO CDE project architecture and requirements definition workshops

A record of the slides used to structure the multi-partner requirements definition workshops held as part of this project are embedded in the files below.

PML | Plymouth Marine Laboratory

Research excellence supporting a sustainable ocean

Constructing Digital Environments;
Generating FAIR data from high resolution sensors in the Western Channel Observatory

Architecture design & requirements elicitation workshop
29th March 2023 | v1.1

PML | Plymouth Marine Laboratory

Research excellence supporting a sustainable ocean

Constructing Digital Environments;
Generating FAIR data from high resolution sensors in the Western Channel Observatory

Architecture design & requirements elicitation workshop 2
15th May 2023 | v1.1

Annex 3 - Validated Discovery Metadata Example

An example of a validated discovery metadata file is embedded in the file below.

l4__uk_ctd_profile_data_99cd4ab963b7b6801716876113b958bb.xml